

Methanol Sensing using Catalyst Free Nickel Foam Modified with Solvo-thermally Synthesized Magnetite (Fe₃O₄) Nanoparticles

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In the present study, methanol has been detected by studying variation in the area enclosed in the I-V curve of cyclic voltammograms. Nickel foam modified with magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles prepared by solvo-thermal method was utilized as a working electrode. X-ray diffraction analysis has been accomplished for the prepared working electrode and it affirms the pure polycrystalline phase of Fe₃O₄ along with nickel peaks. Magnetic measurements (M-H curve) for nanoparticles of Fe₃O₄ records the value of saturation magnetization to be 53 emu/g. Cyclic voltammetric study for prepared electrode has been used to detect methanol present in an electrolyte solution. Corresponding results reveal that the addition of 100 μM of methanol in alkaline electrolyte consisting of 1M NaOH causes a substantial increment in the area enclosed in the I-V curve. Moreover, an increase in value of scan rate of voltage admits enhancement in area enclosed in I-V curve and peak currents as well. Results obtained can be used to develop a handheld biosensor for methanol.

Keywords: Magnetite, Sensing, Nanoparticles, cyclic voltammograms, Verwey transition

Introduction

Magnetite (Fe₃O₄) as one of the oldest magnetic materials possesses an inverse spinel crystal structure. Owing to unique magnetic properties like the highest known Curie temperature (860 K), 100% spin polarizability and good conductivity at room temperature among the ferrites, Fe₃O₄ has been studied extensively for possible candidates in spintronic devices. At low temperatures magnetite undergoes a first-order transition, namely, Verwey transition (T_v), located at T_v ~ 115-125 K depending on sample conditions, whose physical nature has not yet been fully understood¹. Due to facile synthesis options, biocompatibility, intoxicity

and remarkable catalytic activity of Fe₃O₄, nowadays, it became a rising choice for bio-sensing applications². In recent years, electrochemical biosensors based upon Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have been explored extensively. A complete study of amperometric determination of bisphenol A (BPA) was reported by Yu *et al.* by using chitosan-Fe₃O₄ (CS-Fe₃O₄) nanocomposite modified glassy carbon electrodes and it was found that low detection limit, high sensitivity, improved stability, and repeatability were name to be a few outcomes³. Selective electrochemical sensing of arsenite in water has been accomplished by Devi *et al.* using a glassy carbon electrode modified with noble metal-free reduced graphene oxide-Fe₃O₄

nanocomposite via square wave anodic stripping voltammetry (SWASV)⁴. In their study, the enhanced electrochemical performance was reported with a sensitivity of 0.281 $\mu\text{A/ppb}$ and a theoretical limit of detection of 0.12 ppb towards arsenite. Lately, Ni foam modified with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles also came out to play an important role in electrochemical sensing of various pollutants due to the availability of large electro-active sites present in Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles entrapped within pores of Ni foam.

Methanol, also known as wood alcohol is, very important as it is immeasurably utilized in various fields like in chemical synthesis, as clean burning-fuel, as automobile antifreeze, and in rendering ethyl alcohol unfit for drinking, and so on. Due to its uptake on a large scale, the toxicity of methanol has been explored for safety intentions and it was found to be a dangerous poison causing life-threatening diseases⁵. On account of its toxicity, methanol sensing has been delved into much depth and published in several studies. Most of the studies included sensing mechanisms of methanol in its gaseous form⁶. In our study, methanol sensing was accomplished by performing cyclic voltammetric measurements using nickel foam modified with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles as a working electrode.

Experimental

Materials

The experiment has been performed with iron (III) chloride (FeCl_3) (98%) purchased from CDH and urea extra-pure crystals obtained from Merck. The solvent involved was prepared by mixing Rankem-made ethylene glycol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2$) and ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$). Oleylamine micelles were utilized within the synthesis and bought from CDH. All the

chemicals were used as received without any further purification.

Fabrication of electrode

Synthesis involves the preparation of a precursor solution by adding a stoichiometric measure of Fe_3O_4 in solvent prepared by mixing ethanol and ethylene glycol. Urea and oleylamine have been included further with continuous stirring. Ni foam of known dimensions was added in solution and further treated solvothermally for 15 hours in stainless steel autoclave. Subsequently, Ni foam coated with magnetite nanoparticles ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$) was washed and dried further to be utilized as a working electrode (Figure. 1)⁷.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram representing synthesis process of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ working electrode.

Structural investigations were finished with an X-ray Diffractometer (XRD) (Make: Rigaku, Model: Smart lab 3kW) operated at 40kV/30mA with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation (1.5406 $\text{\AA}$) followed by magnetic measurements using a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) (Quantum Design, USA; Model: VersaLab, 3Tesla). Electrochemical studies were performed by using a three-electrode system in Metrohm auto lab (PGSTAT 304 N) constituted of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ as a working electrode, platinum rod as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode in the electrolyte solution of 1M NaOH (Figure. 2).

Fig.2. Schematic representation of three-electrode system.

Results and discussion

Structural analysis:

Structural characterization performed via an X-ray diffractometer proclaimed the formation of a single-phase nanocrystalline magnetite (Fe_3O_4). Figures 3a shows the XRD plot associated with bare nickel foam and nickel foam modified with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. Also, an enlarged view of the XRD plot portraying clear sight of peaks belonging to Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles was shown in figure 3b. As seen in the graph 3a, characteristic peaks of Fe_3O_4 (marked as '#') were indexed at different 2θ values as (220), (311), (400), (511), and (440), respectively and belongs to space group $\text{Fd}\bar{3}\text{m}$ (JCPDS card no. 00-019-0629).

Fig. 3. (a) XRD plot for bare Ni foam and electrode consisting of Ni foam modified with magnetite nanoparticles, (b) Enlarged view of XRD plot revealing peaks of Fe_3O_4 .

Along with peaks of Fe_3O_4 , there are other peaks indexed as (111), (200), and (220) at 2θ values (marked as '*') of 44.76° , 52.1° and 76.58° , respectively can also be observed with strong intensities and were assigned to Nickel foam substrate. The lattice parameter of Fe_3O_4 was also evaluated using 2θ values and noted to be $8.4056 \text{ \AA}$, claiming the formation of a defect-free phase of magnetite with a balanced stoichiometric ratio of Fe:O and was in agreement with JCPDS card no. 00-019-0629⁸.

Magnetic Properties

Magnetic properties for the prepared Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were recorded at room temperature by employing Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) and plotted graph for magnetization vs the applied magnetic field (Oe) showed in figure 4a. The obtained M-H loop achieved the saturation magnetization (M_s) of 53 emu/g and a very low coercivity value of 85 Oe was also estimated (inset of figure 4a). The value of saturation

magnetization 53 emu/g is much lower than that of bulk saturation magnetization value of 90 emu/g and may be due to the anisotropy in crystal, irregular arrangement of sub-lattices, or variation in particles size. Also, the existence of a magnetic dead layer around the surface of the nanoparticles contributes to a reduction in the saturation magnetization value^{9, 10}.

Fig. 4. (a) Magnetization vs. Magnetic Field plot for Fe_3O_4 (with an inset picture depicting hysteresis loop and coercivity), (b) Normalized Magnetization vs. Temperature curve showing Verwey transition for Fe_3O_4 .

To explore the magnetic behavior at low temperature, normalized magnetization viz. $M(T)/M(50\text{K})$ vs temperature were scanned also and strikingly, rarest characteristic property, Verwey Transition (VT) for Fe_3O_4 was evidenced near 110 K (figure 4b). At Verwey transition temperature (T_V), a sudden increase in magnetization value exhibited due to Jahn-Teller distortion involving perturbed distortion of cubic spinel structure into the monoclinic structure by Fe^{3+} ions of octahedral sites in Fe_3O_4 ¹¹. Depending upon variation in parameters of synthesis of Fe_3O_4 viz. temperature, cationic distributions, oxygen deficiency, etc. different values of T_V have been accounted within the range of 120 K-80K. In our case, VT appeared at a T_V value of 110 K due to one of the possible reasons.

Electrochemical Measurements

Prepared $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ electrode was used for detection of 100 μM concentration of methanol in alkaline medium constituting of 1M of NaOH solution via cyclic voltammetry (CV). Figure 5a shows the CV curve of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ performed in 1M of NaOH solution with 0 μM and 100 μM concentration of methanol (CH_3OH) at a scan rate of 80 mV/s. The appearance of redox peaks in both cases was ascribed to the charge transfer process of solid-state redox. Upon the addition of methanol, the CV curve admitted approximately enhancement of ~38 % in both oxidation and reduction current. A quite large enhancement in oxidation and reduction current appeared because Fe_3O_4 being a hub of large electro-active sites causes feasible electro-oxidation of methanol.

Fig. 5. (a) Cyclic voltammograms of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ electrode with $0 \mu\text{M}$ and $100 \mu\text{M}$ concentrations of methanol, (b) Magnetite modified nickel foam electrode at scan rate of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 mV/s; inset showing variation in peak current at different scan rates.

Here, Fe_3O_4 acted as a catalyst for electro-oxidation of methanol, and the mechanism during the process involves adsorption of reactants on the surface of Fe_3O_4 and then conversion in intermediated species, and lastly the formation of products^{12, 13}. Figure 5b depicts CV investigation of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ electrode as a function of scan rate from 20 mV/s to 100 mV/s with an interval of 20 mV/s and it can be

estimated that magnitude of both reduction and oxidation current increases rapidly with scan rate (inset) signaling better improved catalytic behavior of electrode.

Conclusions

To summarize, working electrode $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ has been successfully synthesized via the facile single-step solvothermal method and structural analysis declared synthesis of pure crystalline spinel phase of Fe_3O_4 on Ni foam substrate. Lattice parameter value was $8.4056 \text{ \AA}$ which exacted the formation of the defect-free phase of Fe_3O_4 . The low value of saturation magnetization of 53 emu/g was recorded and departure from bulk value was explained on the basis of the presence of magnetically dead layer hindering exchange interaction among the surface of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and core spin. Methanol sensing is done via observing variation in redox currents of cyclic voltammograms which amazingly, acknowledged about $\sim 38\%$ enhancement in both oxidation and reduction current upon addition of $100 \mu\text{M}$ of methanol. Electro-oxidation of methanol was assigned as the reason for enhancement in current values and $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ was found to be acting as a catalyst in electro-oxidation. The present study demonstrated primary outcomes of methanol sensing and results are inevitably interesting for the fabrication of biosensor for methanol using $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NF}$ as a working electrode.

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